

GLOBAL THREATS

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Abstract

In this scientific paper the main topic is related to the issue of global problems, which one day in the future will affect life and the entire planet earth. This problem of global issues is (problem, risk) that negatively affects the global community and environment, with catastrophic proportions, including environmental issues, political crisis, health crisis, social issues and economic crisis. Solutions to global issues generally require cooperation between nations. Bhargava, Vinay (2006), Hite and Seitz, point out in their book *Global Issues*, (2012) that global issues are defined differently from international issues, and that the former arise from the growing international interdependence, which makes the issues themselves interdependent. I do not understand that our interconnectedness on global issues sometimes makes us feel more vulnerable to global catastrophes, rather than making us more adaptable to our circumstances. I ask myself, is the human factor the main cause of climate change? I would never claim that man is the main destroyer of nature and climate change, with his reckless actions that one day the planet earth will become uninhabitable.

Keywords: global, planet, temperature, man, climate,

INTRODUKTION

It suffices to list the titles of the paper more briefly and we are convinced of the clarity, academic fluency, scientific competence, cognitive, research, argumentative values and the areas where the trend of globalization is spreading and is rapidly appearing in the world. During this research I have expressed in an understandable language and illustrated with works or quotations of authors in a contemporary voice where I would single out Abu-Lughod, Jannat (1991), James, Paul (2005), Martell, Luke (2010), Hite and Seitz, (2012) emphasize in their book "Global Issues of the first steps or indicators of globalization, the evolution on which it has developed. According to Hite and Seitz, (2012) emphasize in their book "Global Issues", that global issues are considered different from international issues, and that the former arise from international interdependence which is growing, which makes the issues themselves interdependent. I do not understand that our interconnectedness on global issues sometimes makes us feel more vulnerable to global catastrophes, rather than making us more adaptable to our circumstances. Of interest and very worrying are the environment and global warming and climate problems that pose global threats such as human impact on the environment, water scarcity, global warming, global catastrophic risk, solar and volcanic activity, livelihoods, climate change mitigation. Clean energy, the international climate agreement, concluding, the paper *Globalism and the challenges of the XXI century*, is a paper of theoretical interest, study, with general values for global decision-making, is an added value in the economic and social literature in Kosovo, presents a serious commitment and accumulated work, which in a

synthesized way presents aspects of globalization, causes and ways of manifestation, as well as its challenges today and in the future. This paper is the first impetus for me but also for other researchers to engage and contribute to other work with this object or even for specific issues of global threats, which endanger planet earth.

Literature Review: During the preparation of this scientific paper I have used academic literature from internationally renowned judges who dealt with this issue which is very troubling to humanity, citing authors such as: Bhargava, Vinay (2006), Global Issues 3. "Global Issues (2012), Preface", Hotchkiss, Michael (2014-12-01), Bostrom, Nick. Ripple WJ, Wolf C, NewsomeTM, Galetti M, Alamgir M, Crist E, Mahmoud MI, Laurance WF (November 13, 2017), Bostrom, Nick Ripple WJ, Wolf C, NewsomeTM, Galetti M, Alamgir M, Crist E, Mahmoud MI, Laurance WF 13 November 2017), .IPCC SR15 Ch1 2018, p. 54: These global-level rates of human-driven change far exceed the rates of change driven by geophysical or biosphere forces that have altered the Earth System trajectory in the past...

Object of the study: The object of the study is related to global warming which poses a danger or threat to the globe, therefore the object of the study is related to the topic of this nature, which is quite worrying recently as we have an enormous increase in temperature, so the object of my study is focused on what are the causes of global warming, and what measures should be taken in the future to alleviate the current situation which remains a challenge for humanity. To prove the saying that man is the main factor of global warming and climate change, we refer to the statements of world climate academics who based on scientific research made from 10 thousand abstracts had come to the conclusion that 95% of their abstracts, was with the same content and opinions that man is the main factor of climate change and global warming.

Methodology: During the research of this topic in this scientific paper which is quite serious and disturbing for the globe, I used comparative methods. Contemporary climate change includes global warming and its effects on Earth's weather patterns. If we refer to the comparative method there have been previous periods of climate change, but the current changes are significantly faster and not for natural causes. Instead, they are caused by the emission of greenhouse gases, mainly carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane.

Combustion of fossil fuels for energy use generates most of these emissions. Agriculture, steel production, cement production and forest loss are additional resources. Greenhouse gases are transparent to sunlight, allowing it to heat the Earth's surface. When the Earth emits that heat as infrared radiation, gases absorb it, trapping heat near the Earth's surface. As the planet warms, it causes changes such as the loss of snow cover that reflects sunlight, amplifying global warming.

Contemporary **climate change** includes both **global warming** and its impacts on Earth's weather patterns. There have been previous periods of climate change, but the current changes are distinctly more rapid and not due to natural causes. Instead, they are caused by the emission of greenhouse gases, mostly carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane. Burning fossil fuels for energy use creates most of these emissions. Agriculture, steelmaking, cement production, and forest loss are additional sources Greenhouse gases are transparent to sunlight, allowing it through to heat the Earth's surface. When the Earth emits that heat

as infrared radiation the gases absorb it, trapping the heat near the Earth's surface. As the planet heats up it causes changes like the loss of sunlight-reflecting snow cover, amplifying global warming.

On land, temperatures have risen about twice as fast as the global average. Deserts are expanding, while heat waves and wildfires are becoming more common. Increased warming in the Arctic has contributed to melting permafrost, glacial retreat and sea ice loss. Higher temperatures are also causing more intense storms and other weather extremes. Rapid environmental change in mountains, coral reefs, and the Arctic is forcing many species to relocate or become extinct. Climate change threatens people with food and water scarcity, increased flooding, extreme heat, more disease, and economic loss. Human migration and conflict can be a result. The World Health Organization (WHO) calls climate change the greatest threat to global health in the 21st century. Even if efforts to minimise future warming are successful, some effects will continue for centuries. These include sea level rise, and warmer, more acidic oceans.

Fig.1 Average surface air temperatures from 2011 to 2020 compared to the 1951–1980 average

Many of these impacts are already felt at the current 1.2 °C (2.2 °F) level of warming. Additional warming will increase these impacts and may trigger tipping points, such as the melting of the Greenland ice sheet. Under the 2015 Paris Agreement, nations collectively agreed to keep warming "well under 2 °C". However, with pledges made under the Agreement, global warming would still reach about 2.7 °C (4.9 °F) by the end of the century. Limiting warming to 1.5 °C will require halving emissions by 2030 and achieving net-zero emissions by 2050.

Fig.2 Change in average surface air temperature since the industrial revolution, plus drivers for that change. Human activity has caused increased temperatures, with natural forces adding some variability, SPM-7

Making deep cuts in emissions will require switching away from burning fossil fuels and towards using electricity generated from low-carbon sources. This includes phasing out coal-fired power plants, vastly increasing use of wind, solar, and other types of renewable energy, switching to electric vehicles, switching to heat pumps in buildings, and taking measures to conserve energy. Carbon can also be removed from the atmosphere, for instance by increasing forest cover. While communities may adapt to climate change through efforts like better coastline protection, they cannot avert the risk of severe, widespread, and permanent impacts.

Before the 1980s, it was unclear whether warming by increased greenhouse gases would dominate aerosol-induced cooling. Scientists then often used the term inadvertent climate modification to refer to the human impact on the climate. In the 1980s, the terms global warming and climate change were popularised. The former refers only to increase surface warming, the latter describes the full effect of greenhouse gases on the climate. Global warming became the most popular term after NASA climate scientist James Hansen used it in his 1988 testimony in the U.S. Senate. In the 2000s, the term climate change increased in popularity. Global warming usually refers to human-induced warming of the Earth system, whereas climate change can refer to natural or anthropogenic change. The two terms are often used interchangeably. Various scientists, politicians and media figures have adopted the terms climate crisis or climate emergency to talk about climate change, and global heating instead of global warming. The policy editor-in-chief of The Guardian said they included this language in their editorial guidelines "to ensure that we are being scientifically precise, while also communicating clearly with readers on this very important issue". In 2019, Oxford Languages chose climate emergency as its word of the year, defining it as "a situation in which urgent action is required to reduce or halt climate change and avoid potentially irreversible environmental damage resulting from it".

Fig.3 Climate change is driven by rising greenhouse gas levels in the atmosphere. This strengthens the greenhouse effect which traps heat in Earth's climate system.

Fig.4 Global surface temperature reconstruction over the last 2000 years using proxy data from tree rings, corals, and ice cores in blue. Directly observed data is in red.

Multiple independent instrumental datasets show that the climate system is warming. The 2011–2020 decade warmed to an average 1.09 °C [0.95–1.20 °C] compared to the pre-industrial baseline (1850–1900).[32] Surface temperatures are rising by about 0.2 °C per decade, with 2020 reaching a temperature of 1.2 °C above the pre-industrial era. Since 1950, the number of cold days and nights has decreased, and the number of warm days and nights has increased. There was little net warming between the 18th century and the mid-19th century. Climate information for that period comes from climate proxies, such as trees and ice cores. Thermometer records began to provide global coverage around 1850. Historical patterns of warming and cooling, like the Medieval Climate Anomaly and the Little Ice Age, did not occur at the same time across different regions. Temperatures may have reached as high as those of the late-20th century in a limited set of regions. There have been prehistorical episodes of global warming, such as the Paleocene–Eocene Thermal Maximum. However, the modern observed rise in temperature and CO₂ concentrations has been so rapid that even abrupt geophysical events in Earth's history do not approach current rates. Evidence of warming from air temperature measurements are reinforced with a wide range of other observations. There has been an increase in the frequency and intensity of heavy precipitation, melting of snow and land ice, and increased atmospheric humidity. Flora and fauna are also behaving in a manner consistent with warming; for instance, plants are flowering earlier in spring. Another key

indicator is the cooling of the upper atmosphere, which demonstrates that greenhouse gases are trapping heat near the Earth's surface and preventing it from radiating into space.

Regional aspects to temperature rises, Regions of the world warm at differing rates. The pattern is independent of where greenhouse gases are emitted, because the gases persist long enough to diffuse across the planet. Since the pre-industrial period, the average surface temperature over land regions has increased almost twice as fast as the global-average surface temperature. This is because of the larger heat capacity of oceans, and because oceans lose more heat by evaporation. The thermal energy in the global climate system has grown with only brief pauses since at least 1970, and over 90% of this extra energy has been stored in the ocean. The rest has heated the atmosphere, melted ice, and warmed the continents. The Northern Hemisphere and the North Pole have warmed much faster than the South Pole and Southern Hemisphere. The Northern Hemisphere not only has much more land, but also more seasonal snow cover and sea ice. As these surfaces flip from reflecting a lot of light to being dark after the ice has melted, they start absorbing more heat. Local black carbon deposits on snow and ice also contribute to Arctic warming. Arctic temperatures are increasing at over twice the rate of the rest of the world. Melting of glaciers and ice sheets in the Arctic disrupts ocean circulation, including a weakened Gulf Stream, further changing the climate.

Drivers of recent temperature rise, The climate system experiences various cycles on its own which can last for years (such as the El Niño–Southern Oscillation), decades or even centuries. Other changes are caused by an imbalance of energy that is "external" to the climate system, but not always external to the Earth. Examples of external forcings include changes in the concentrations of greenhouse gases, solar luminosity, volcanic eruptions, and variations in the Earth's orbit around the Sun.

Fig.5 Drivers of climate change from 1850–1900 to 2010–2019. There was no significant contribution from internal variability or solar and volcanic drivers.

To determine the human contribution to climate change, known internal climate variability and natural external forcings need to be ruled out. A key approach is to determine unique "fingerprints" for all potential causes, then compare these fingerprints with observed patterns of climate change. For example, solar forcing can be ruled out as a major cause. Its fingerprint

would be warming in the entire atmosphere. Yet, only the lower atmosphere has warmed, consistent with greenhouse gas forcing. Attribution of recent climate change shows that the main driver is elevated greenhouse gases, with aerosols having a dampening effect.

Humans

The effects of climate change on humans have been observed worldwide. They are mostly due to warming and shifts in precipitation. Impacts can now be observed on all continents and ocean regions, with low-latitude, less developed areas facing the greatest risk. Continued warming has potentially “severe, pervasive and irreversible impacts” for people and ecosystems. The risks are unevenly distributed, but are generally greater for disadvantaged people in developing and developed countries.

Fig.6 The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (2021) projects that extreme weather will be progressively more common as the Earth warms.

Scientific consensus

There is a near-complete scientific consensus that the climate is warming and that this is caused by human activities. As of 2019, agreement in recent literature reached over 99%. No scientific body of national or international standing disagrees with this view. Consensus has further developed that some form of action should be taken to protect people against the impacts of climate change. National science academies have called on world leaders to cut global emissions.

Scientific discussion takes place in journal articles that are peer-reviewed. Scientists assess these every few years in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change reports. The 2021 IPCC Assessment Report stated that it is "unequivocal" that climate change is caused by humans.

Fig.7 Academic studies of scientific consensus reflect that the level of consensus correlates with expertise in climate science.

Food and health

The WHO has classified climate change as the greatest threat to global health in the 21st century. Extreme weather leads to injury and loss of life, and crop failures to undernutrition. Various infectious diseases are more easily transmitted in a warmer climate, such as dengue fever and malaria. Young children are the most vulnerable to food shortages. Both children and older people are vulnerable to extreme heat. The World Health Organization (WHO) has estimated that between 2030 and 2050, climate change would cause around 250,000 additional deaths per year. They assessed deaths from heat exposure in elderly people, increases in diarrhea, malaria, dengue, coastal flooding, and childhood undernutrition. Over 500,000 more adult deaths are projected yearly by 2050 due to reductions in food availability and quality.

Climate change is affecting food security. It has caused reduction in global yields of maize, wheat, and soybeans between 1981 and 2010. Future warming could further reduce global yields of major crops. Crop production will probably be negatively affected in low-latitude countries, while effects at northern latitudes may be positive or negative. Up to an additional 183 million people worldwide, particularly those with lower incomes, are at risk of hunger as a consequence of these impacts. Climate change also impacts fish populations. Globally, less will be available to be fished.[190] Regions dependent on glacier water, regions that are already dry, and small islands have a higher risk of water stress due to climate change.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion catastrophic global danger is a hypothetical event of the future that could harm human well-being globally, even destroying modern civilization. An event that can cause the extinction of humanity or permanently and drastically limit the potential of humanity is known as an existential danger. Our World in Data, 18 September (2020), citing potential global catastrophic risks include anthropogenic, man-made hazards (technology, governance, climate change) and natural or external hazards, Ripple WJ, Wolf C, Newsome TM , Galetti M,

Alamgir M, Crist E, Mahmoud MI, Laurance WF (November 13, 2017), some examples of technology threats are hostile artificial intelligence and destructive biotechnology or nanotechnology. Misgovernment or malice of global life poses social and political risks to a global war, including nuclear holocaust, bioterrorism, the use of genetically modified organisms, cyberterrorism that destroys critical infrastructure such as the grid, or failure to manage a pandemic. Natural, the current case with the covid-19 pandemic which swept across the globe. Problems and risks in the field of land system, include global warming, environmental degradation, species extinction, famine due to improper resource allocation, human overcrowding, crop failures in agriculture as unsustainable, examples of non-hazardous human are asteroids, a super volcano eruption, the long-term destructive geomagnetic storm of electro nautical devices, climate change, extra-terrestrials, or the prediction of the transformation of a giant red star hitting Earth.

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